

Controlled enrichment of catalysts on the ionic liquid interfaces

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ABSTRACT: (Word Style “BD_Abstract”). All manuscripts must be accompanied by an abstract. The abstract should briefly state the problem or purpose of the research, indicate the theoretical or experimental plan used, summarize the principal findings, and point out the major conclusions. Abstract length is one paragraph

Interfaces of ionic liquids (ILs), which are salts with melting points typically below 100 °C and often below room temperature, play an important role in many current and prospective application areas such as in lubrication,¹⁻³ gas separation,^{4,5} extraction,⁶⁻⁹ and energy storage^{1,10} technologies. In the important field of catalysis, taking advantage of the unique physico-chemical properties of ILs, two new concepts have evolved: Supported Ionic Liquid Phase (SILP)¹¹⁻¹³ and Solid Catalyst with Ionic Liquid Layer (SCILL)¹²⁻¹⁴, both of which are based on coating high-surface-area porous supports with thin IL films. Particularly in SILP, the best of two worlds are combined. Namely, a highly selective homogeneous catalyst is dissolved in a non-volatile IL film on a stationary heterogeneous support.^{2,15,16} Notably, in a typical SILP system, the liquid-gas (LG) interface represents a major fraction of the total reaction volume. However, this interfacial layer may differ considerably in composition and molecular orientation from the isotropic bulk IL.¹⁷ In addition, this layer can influence the behavior and outcome of chemical reactions due to the asymmetric nature of the interface.¹⁸⁻²⁰

These specific properties of the LG interface could be utilized to optimize SILP systems and resolve the common issues with reaction selectivity, yield, and long-term stability in catalysis.²¹ Controlling the environment of the catalyst would provide a handle for the chemistry of the reaction, which, in combination with the fast dynamics of the LG interface, could be beneficial for the overall turn-over frequency particularly in cases of low bulk solubilities of reactants. However, such control would require the development of catalysts that are preferentially positioned at the LG interface in a desired orientation. To the best of our knowledge, this type of control over the enrichment of catalytic reactants has not been achieved thus far.

One can envisage that the catalyst placement and orientation could be regulated by the choice of IL. For example, non-fluorinated ILs are known to form bulk nanostructures consisting of polar and nonpolar domains, while ILs with fluorinated alkyl chains typically exhibit additional agglomeration of nonpolar, fluorine-rich moieties.^{22,23} This property was recently used to achieve LG surface enrichment in IL mixtures. Specifically, as determined by angle-resolved X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (ARXPS), the partially fluorinated alkyl chain of [PFBMIm][PF₆] preferentially enriched at the IL/vacuum (LV) interface de-homogenizing the mixture with its non-fluorinated analogue [C₄C₁Im][PF₆].²⁴ The selective enrichment was more pronounced with decreasing [PFBMIm][PF₆] content and with decreasing temperature, an effect that was also clearly discernable in the follow-up measurements of surface tension in these mixtures.²⁵ While a detailed molecular understanding of these phenomena is still missing, these studies suggest that fluorinated alkyl chains could be excellent functional groups to manipulate the position of a catalyst within the film. We therefore hypothesize that attaching fluorinated moieties to the ligands could secure the enrichment of the catalysts at the LG interface. In turn, this should improve the exposure of the catalyst to the reactants and hence the reaction rate, ultimately increasing SILP performance.

To test our hypothesis, we devise a comprehensive modeling approach based on molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, the latter being a proven tool for studies of IL interfaces.²⁶⁻³⁰ MD simulations so far were able to recapitulate molecular orientation at the LG interface,^{31,32,33} and relate them to the surface tension through the “Langmuir principle”^{34,35}. Simulations were furthermore used to understand the nanostructure of IL mixtures,^{36,37,38} although hitherto the respective LG interfaces were only scarcely analysed by theoretical tools.²⁷⁻⁴⁰ We here address this issue and first perform MD simulations of mixtures of [PFBMIm][PF₆] with [C₄C₁Im][PF₆] to study enrichment effects of the fluorinated alky chains at the LG interfaces. This allows us to validate our models against the analogous experiments and in turn provide detailed molecular insight in observed enrichment and surface tension.

Subsequently, we attempt to manipulate the positioning of Wilkinson-like catalysts within the film. These catalysts are often used in the context of hydrogenation of unsaturated hydrocarbons in ILs,^{35,41} including SILP⁴². Our investigations of the surface localization of the Wilkinson catalyst, RhCl(PPh₃)₃, and its fluorinated counterpart, RhCl(P(Ph-CF₂-CF₃)₃)₃, yield a much stronger localization of the latter at the LG interface, which results in an increased exposure of the rhodium atom to potential reactants from the gas phase. Hence, these results can be viewed as a proof of principle for catalyst surface enrichment, which is the first step in the development of the new generation of highly efficient SILP systems.

In order to simulate mixtures with increasing content of [PFBMIm][PF₆] in [C₄C₁Im][PF₆] (molar fractions of 0, 0.1, 0.5, 0.75, 1) we first parametrized our ions (Fig. 1a) and built a 8-9 nm thick IL slab (Fig. 1b) containing a total of 1400 ion pairs, with 34 nm thick layers of vacuum on both sides (see Supplementary Information (SI) for all methodological details). Each system is consequently equilibrated and finally simulated for 200 ns at the desired temperature ($T = 300, 320, 350, 370$ K) using the GROMACS framework. The ensuing analysis of the recorded trajectories allowed us to reconstruct the density profile of each IL ion throughout the system (SI-Fig.S1) and explore the dynamic behavior of the LV interface.

We benchmark our simulations against ARXPS experiments of identical mixtures of [PFBMIm][PF₆] and [C₄C₁Im][PF₆].²⁴ In ARXPS, importantly, it is possible to detect the nitrogen (N_{Im}) associated with imidazolium rings in both cations. Furthermore, the fluorine atoms of the anion (F_{PF_6}) can be distinguished from those of the fluorinated alkyl-chains (F_{CFX}). With the kinetic energy of 790 eV F 1s electrons have a characteristic inelastic mean free path λ is 1.9 nm at normal emission (0°) nm⁴³. At grazing emission (80°), λ for F 1s electrons decreases to 0.32 nm, making the measurement very surface sensitive. For N 1s electrons $\lambda = 2.5$ nm at normal emission (0°), and 0.42 nm at grazing emission. By quantitative analysis (including all core levels), it is thus possible to determine the composition of the outermost surface layer, as compared to the bulk. In particular, the surface enrichment of the [PFBMIm]⁺ cations relative to the [PF₆]⁻ anions, and the average orientation of the [PFBMIm]⁺ cations at the surface can be extracted.²⁴ For quantification, we define the surface enrichment factor (EF) for different species (F_{CFX} , F_{PF_6} , and N_{Im}) by normalizing the signal intensity measured in the surface-sensitive 80° geometry by the known bulk stoichiometry,²⁴ whereby $EF=1$ corresponds to the bulk composition. These data can be directly compared to MD simulations from atomic density profiles $g(z)$, obtained from the data using the previously described methodology (see SI for details).⁴⁴ In short, EF is calculated by integrating $g(z)$ up to λ from the interface (first inflection point in $g(z)$), with the appropriate stoichiometric factor as in the case of the experimental analogue. Although a further improved analysis of the experimental data could be achieved by accounting for the attenuation of the ARXPS signal,³⁵ this simple and robust procedure provides reasonably accurate results, and allow for consistent analysis of the entire theoretical dataset (see Fig. SX). However, the current approach reports data that are not biased by the experimental attenuation, and is thus expected to systematically report higher EF .

With the simulations being in very good agreement with experiments (Fig. 1b), our result show that the lower the molar fraction of [PFBMIm][PF₆] in the mixture, the more pronounced is the surface enrichment of the fluorinated chain of [PFBMIm]⁺ relative to the bulk composition. At the same time, no particular enrichment effects are observed for the [PF₆]⁻ or [C₄C₁Im]⁺. Pronounced orientation of the fluorinated chains towards the vacuum is observed in MD simulations even for neat [PFBMIm][PF₆] with the EF value around 1.5 for F_{CFX} and also in the surface-sensitive 80° ARXP spectra. Upon decreasing the temperature, the surface enrichment of [PFBMIm]⁺ in the mixtures is further enhanced, both in simulations and the experiments (SI-Fig.S3). These observations confirm the strong entropic effects in the organization of the interface.²⁴ The increase in enrichment of the fluorinated cation chains was observed by ARXPS down to well below room temperature for the mixtures with [PFBMIm]⁺ contents up to 50 mol%. For the mixture with 75 mol%, however, upon further cooling to 293 K, the surface enrichment of [PFBMIm]⁺ decreased drastically. This drop was attributed to a (partial) precipitation of the pure [PFBMIm][PF₆], and the appearance of a [C₄C₁Im][PF₆]-rich phase at the topmost layer of this mixture is inferred. The enrichment of the [C₄C₁Im]⁺ is also observed in MD simulations below 320 K. However, in these systems the precipitation does not take place, and instead the IL is likely super-cooled, which is evident by the strong increase in viscosities of mixtures where [PFBMIm][PF₆] is a majority fraction at temperatures below 320 K, as previously noted.²⁵

Figure 1. Study of interface composition of $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]:[PFBMim][PF_6]$ mixtures. a) The ions building the two ILs. b) A typical MD simulation system ($[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]:[PFBMim][PF_6]$ at 50:50 mol%), was prepared by iterating vacuum and liquid slabs. With the thickness of 8.5 nm, the liquid phase is sufficient to provide two independent LV interfaces. c) LG interface composition at 370 K, as a function of the $[PFBMim][PF_6]$ content. The top panel displays the enrichment factors for F_{CFX} (black), F_{PF_6} (red) and N_{Im} (green); full and open symbols represent MD simulation and ARXPS data for 80° emission angle, respectively. The bottom panel shows the ratio of F_{CFX} and F_{PF_6} ; experimental data, obtained from emission at 0° and 80° are shown as black and red open diamonds, while the analogous MD simulation data are shown as filled circles. d) Surface tension as a function of the mixture composition. The top panel shows MD simulation results at 300 K (black), 320 (red), 350 (green) and 370 K (blue). Dashed lines are guidance for the eye. The bottom panel shows the variation in the surface tension relative to the tension of the neat $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$. Data from the pendent drop experiments are shown explicitly, while the simulation data are averaged over the four temperatures for each mixture. Error bars represent the variation in the simulation data.

Interestingly, we find that the enrichment of the anion, which is negligible in neat $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$ steadily increases in a temperature independent fashion with the addition of fluorinated IL, and is most pronounced in the neat $[PFBMim][PF_6]$. Somewhat more unexpected, however, is the interplay between the total fraction of fluorinated chains and the relative concentration of the aliphatic alkyl chains at the interface. In particular, more detailed inspection of density profiles (Fig. S1) shows that for neat $[C_4C_1Im][PF_6]$, no particular aggregation of aliphatic alkyl chains is observed at the LG interface. Adding a 10mol% of $[PFBMim][PF_6]$ induces strong interfacial structuring, both of aliphatic alkyl but more of fluorinated alkyl chains (Fig. S2). Cooling this mixture promotes the enrichment of the $[PFBMim]^+$ (minority fraction), while the normalized density profile of $[C_4C_1Im]^+$ (majority fraction) stays mostly unaffected by the temperature change. At 50mol% $[PFBMim][PF_6]$, the trends begin to inverse – cooling does not affect the density profile of $[PFBMim]^+$, but unexpectedly, promotes the $[C_4C_1Im]^+$ on the interface. At 75 mol% $[PFBMim][PF_6]$, the trends are inverted and enrichment of $[PFBMim]^+$ (majority fraction) drops with the lowering the temperature, while the presence of $[C_4C_1Im]^+$ (minority fraction) strongly increases at the LG interface. These results show together that for the mixtures with cations that have fluorinated or aliphatic the alkyl chains, it is the minority fraction that exhibits strong enrichment on the interface, particularly at low temperatures (Figs S3 and S4). Indeed these results are consistent with previous simulations of imidazolium cation in the presence of a nonpolarfluorinated moiety attached to the sulfonate group of the anion $[C_4F_9SO_3]^-$, where the competition between the two chain types has been identified.²²

Scheme 1: Wilkinson's catalysts $\text{RhCl}(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ and its analogue with the phosphine ligand functionalized with a fluorinated alkyl chain, $\text{RhCl}(\text{P}(\text{Ph}_3-\text{CF}_2-\text{CF}_3)_3)_3$. On the left, we show the basic form (left panel) and the two side chains R (middle and right panel, respectively).

alkyl chains for the LG interface^{22,46-48}. In mixtures, where the cation alkyl chain and the fluorinated alkyl chain of the two cations have the same length, as is this paper, a larger concentration of fluorinated groups compared to the concentration of alkyl groups should also lower the surface tension. Indeed, this behavior was recently confirmed by pendant drop experiments at small fractions of $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ in $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ at around 370 K.²⁵ While the neat ILs $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ and $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ exhibit surface tensions σ of 38.3 and 29.8 $\text{mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$, respectively, a pronounced decrease is already seen in mixtures with small molar bulk contents of 0.03 ($\sigma = 36.7 \text{ mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$) and 0.09 ($\sigma = 35.9 \text{ mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$) $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$. This decrease from neat $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ to neat $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ is associated with the increased overall concentration of fluorinated chains at the LG interface.²⁵

To compare with these data, we first calculate the ST directly from the pressure-pressure correlations, using the GROMACS built-in tool (top panel in Fig. 1d). The extracted STs are, however, systematically smaller than the values obtained in MD and pendant drop measurements.²⁵ This alteration arises likely from the fact that charges of all ions were scaled by a factor of 0.9 from their nominal force field value. While this scaling particularly affects the surface tension, it is introduced since it provides the best compromise in recovering static and dynamic properties simultaneously in bulk and interfacial ILs.²⁷ Furthermore, to account for the differences in temperature between simulations and experiments, and to emphasize the common trends observed in simulations at different temperatures (bottom panel, Fig. 1d), we calculate, the relative variation of ST as derived from MD and pendant drop measurements (bottom panel, Fig. 2d).

Figure 2. Optimizing the position of the catalyst at LG interface of a SILP system. a) Number density profiles of $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ (magenta) are shown with the rhodium number density (dashed lines, multiplied by 60) of in $(\text{RhCl}(\text{PPh}_3)_3)$ (left) and $(\text{RhCl}(\text{PPh}_3-\text{F}_6-\text{F}_9)_3)$ (right). In the background, we present a cut through the liquid and the relevant catalyst b) Potential of mean force $F(z)$ for bringing a catalyst ($\text{RhCl}(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ in cyan and $\text{RhCl}(\text{PPh}_3-\text{F}_6-\text{F}_9)_3$ in orange) across the LG interface into the bulk IL. For orientation, the number density of the IL is also provided (magenta). The inset shows the top view on the LG interface. Exposed rhodium (red) and fluorine (orange) atoms are shown together with the rest of the catalysts (cyan).

Here the difference in ST of a mixture and the neat $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ is normalized by the ST of neat $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$ at the appropriate temperature (bottom panel in Fig. 1d). The relative change of ST agrees very well with the experiments in the relevant regime.²⁵

We find that surface tension decreases continuously with increasing molar fraction of $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$, likely because the absolute concentration of the fluorinated chains steadily increases. We also observe that for molar fractions of $[\text{PFBMIm}][\text{PF}_6]$ larger than 50 mol% there is a change in slope, independent of temperature. This modification of the trend is likely related to the interplay between the dominant fraction, which changes from being hydrophobic to fluorophobic at 50 mol%. This couples with the enrichment of minority fraction increases from the 50 mol%. The different slopes emerge because the fluorinated chains in the liquid with predominantly aliphatic alkyl chains has a somewhat different effect compared to adding aliphatic alkyl chains into a fluid with predominantly fluorinated chains.²²

Now that we gained good understanding of the drivers of interfacial enrichment, we proceed with attempting to design a catalyst that would preferentially be located within the first few IL layers. We start from a standard Wilkinson catalyst, $\text{RhCl}(\text{PPh}_3)_3$, here denoted as catalyst **1** (Scheme 1). $\text{RhCl}(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ is a coordination complex of rhodium, commonly used in hydrogenation of alkenes.^{Ref} To begin with, we first calculate its force field parameters (SI Method section 2) and then immerse it in neat $[\text{C}_4\text{C}_1\text{Im}][\text{PF}_6]$, constructed previously. Upon careful relaxation of the system (see SI Method section 3 for details), we perform a free simulation run (Fig. 2a). We find that within the 200 ns production run, the catalyst does not significantly change its position relative to the interface. It is typically slightly submersed, 0.5 nm away from the inflection point although occasionally approaching the surface (see side (Fig. 2a) and top view in Fig. 2b).

In an attempt to expose the catalyst to the vacuum, we now functionalize the phenyl groups of the catalyst' phosphine ligands with the same fluorinated alkyl chains in para position that are present in $[\text{PFBMIm}]^+$ (right panel in Scheme 1). This gives rise to a rhodium complex, $\text{RhCl}(\text{P}(\text{Ph}-\text{CF}_2-\text{CF}_3)_3)_3$, which we denote as catalyst **2**. At small concentrations, these side chains should drive the catalyst to the interface. As expected, by repeating the same calculations as in the case of $\text{RhCl}(\text{PPh}_3)_3$, we find that this new catalyst shows stronger surface affinity than the standard Wilkinson catalyst. Unlike $\text{RhCl}(\text{PPh}_3)_3$, catalyst **2** actually appears to float on the IL with the rhodium exposed (see top and side view in Fig. 2b). Due to the strong preference of fluorinated chains for the top most layers, the rotational dynamics of the new catalyst are virtually suppressed. The chloride atom systematically points toward the bulk of the liquid (Fig. 3a), while the whole structure remains by and large planar (Fig. 3b). Note that a very similar preferential orientation is also found for catalyst **1**.

Due to the high affinity of the catalysts for the surface, it is, nonetheless, not possible to quantitatively evaluate the enrichment factors from our unrestrained simulations (Fig. 2a). We therefore perform umbrella sampling to calculate the potential of mean force $F(z)$ for transferring the catalyst from the bulk IL over the interface into the vacuum (Fig. 2b). Both for catalysts **2** and **1**, $F(z)$ has a minimum at the same distance from the LV interface, although the rhodium atom displays significantly larger positional fluctuations in **1**. Due to the larger size of the side chains and their functionality, **2** is, however, significantly more exposed to the vacuum. Interestingly, the catalyst **1** associates in the first solvation shell with the IL cation, while **2** exhibits the preference for the fluorinated anion (see SI-Fig.S5). While similar in overall shape, the two $F(z)$ have a significantly different depth of the minimum in the free energy relative to the bulk (ΔF) which is more than double for **2**. In units of thermal energy ($k_B T$, with k_B being the Boltzmann constant), the minimum of **2** is 8.6 $k_B T$, compared to 3.1 $k_B T$ for **1** at room temperature. This difference in the free energy comes from the fact that the solvation of **2** at the LG interface is significantly stronger than the solvation of **1**. This effect is likely related to the capacity of ligands of the catalyst **2** to form fluorine-rich nano-domains with anions at the LG interface, a situation that is inversed in the bulk.

The obtained $F(z)$ is also related to the density profile of the catalyst in the film, which emerges as $g(z) = \exp(-F(z)/k_B T)$. Hence, it is in principle possible to predict the enrichment factors for the two species and eventually probed by ARXPS. Actually, the relatively deep minimum in $F(z)$ suggest that most of the compound **2** should remain at the LG interface, to the extent that some precipitation could take place if there is a surplus in the surface layer. Furthermore, spontaneous transition of **2** into the bulk is unlikely, while being possible for **1**,

Figure 3. Orientation of catalysts. The graph shows the probability distribution of the angle that the Rh-Cl bond closes with the normal on the interface pointing toward the bulk with a sharp maximum at 8°. The inset shows the time evolution of the P-Ru-Cl angle for all 3 ligands. The planar structure as obtained through the geometry optimisation remains stable throughout the MD run.

and orientation of the catalyst could strongly improve the catalytic turn-over frequency which would benefit both from the fast dynamics of the liquid-gas interface and the direct exposure of the catalyst to the reactant. While in the current case, our work provides only the theoretical foundation for the new generation of SILP systems, we expect their laboratory realization in very near future.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. We provide detailed simulation method section, SI Figs. 1-10 and two movies showing the catalysts on the IL interface. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Author Contributions

The project was conceived through contributions of all authors. ASS supervised its execution. NVA performed all simulations and the data analysis. CW parametrized the catalysts. NVA, FM and ASS wrote the first draft. All authors contributed to writing of the final manuscript and have given approval for submission.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Catalyst **1**=RhCl(PPh₃)₃

Catalyst **2**= RhCl(P(Ph-CF₂-CF₃))₃

due to the depth of the minimum. On the contrary, the degradation of the catalyst on the surface could potentially induce the fast recruitment from the bulk, which is a particularly attractive perspective for SILP catalysis.

In conclusion, in this paper we show that, by using appropriate side chains for the functionalization, it is possible to achieve significant surface enrichment in SILP systems. The effect was first demonstrated for IL mixtures, where excellent agreement between the results of experiments and modeling are obtained. We are able to demonstrate that for imidazolium based ILs, addition of fluorinated side chains induces enrichment of fluorinated species at the LG surface, and vice versa. The effect is mostly driven by the interplay between hydrophobicity and fluorophobicity. Utilizing the same idea, we demonstrate that it is possible to functionalize a catalyst and pin it to the very interface of an IL. As a result, the catalytic metal center becomes exposed, due to the strong solvation effects of the IL. In an operational SILP system, such a precise positioning

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